

Indian Annual Budgets: A review with special reference to Budget 2018

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ABSTRACT

The government's annual budget states its priorities. It is an extensive financial statement of the money received and the expenditures over a year. It is imperative to decode the government's annual budget policy as it is linked to improving the quality of life of its citizens. This review has illustrated that India's annual budget concentrates more on the defence sector than health and education. It needs to come up with better strategies to counter its fiscal deficit.

KEYWORDS: Government, Annual Budget, Taxes.

1. INTRODUCTION

The annual budget balances out income against the expenses in twelve months. The yearly governmental budget is a comprehensive financial statement of the money received and the expenditures over a year. It is imperative to decode (read-interpret) the government's annual budget policy as it is linked to improving the quality of life of its citizens (Das, 2007).

The Ministry of Finance prepares the budget after discussion with the other stakeholders like Centre, State, industry representatives, NGO's, etc. and presents the budget as follows: actual figures for the previous year; figures worked out in the budget for the current year and estimate of funding for the coming year (Bhatia, 2016).

The budget is created based on three accounts held by the government: Consolidated Fund, Contingency Fund, and Public Accounts. The consolidated fund has all the revenue received by the government. It is further distributed into the Revenue account, which manages the Expenditures (money spent from the receipts) and Receipts (received by taxation and other receipts). The capital account receives money from borrowed funds and loan recoveries. Expenditures from the capital account are done from these borrowed funds as a liability (Bhatia, 2016).

The contingency fund is for unforeseen circumstances and is at the jurisdiction of the President of India and the Governor of any state. The public account is money collected from deposits, remittances, debts, advances, etc. It is controlled by the Reserve bank of India as the banker of the government (Bhatia, 2016).

In India, the government's expenditure has increased from about 3 lakh crore in 2000 to about 22 lakhs in 2017, i.e. about twenty thousand rupees, is spent per person in India. The money is spread over sectors like defence, agriculture, security, social welfare, education, health, infrastructure, etc. (14th Finance Commission, 2015-20).

In India, most of the expenditure in the annual budget is concentrated on defence, followed by Food, Consumer Affairs, Public Distribution, Rural Development, HRD, Home Affairs, Transport, Tourism and culture, Chemical and Fertilisers, Agriculture, Health and Family welfare and Railways (14th Finance Commission, 2015-20).

The central government in India collects revenue through taxes such as income tax, corporation tax, central GST, and union excise. Forty-two percent of this money is then distributed to the states, and 58% is retained by the central government (14th Finance Commission, 2015-20). The budget formulated before April 2018 showed that at least 24% is spent on paying its interest on the money it has borrowed over the years, about 12% is spent on the subsidies, and seven percent on pensions. A total of forty-three was the Government expenditure till March 2018 (14th Finance Commission, 2015-20).

The issue in India is that the fiscal deficit, i.e. the gap between spending, is higher than its receipts. Presently it is 48.8% of its GDP (2018-2019 budgets). As any government around the world needs to have fiscal pellucidity as it affects the reliability and credibility of the budget (Sarr, 2015), this review plans to study some of the issues related to the government's annual budget.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Fiscal transparency

Fiscal transparency gives way to a more trustworthy budget, thus improving its execution in all sectors of the government's expenditures with better governance; policy-making decisions and their implementation; improved GDP growth; inflation, etc. (Sarr, 2015). The annual budget by the governing Parliament is endorsed by the country's voters in the form of their representation by the Member of Parliament (MP). They, on their behalf, are parties to formulating the budget progression.

But the issue is that a small group of individuals undertakes this process, and the priorities are not made public to everyone, including the voters. The ultimate performance of the budget cannot be assessed transparently. Therefore, the more the voters understand the budget, the less will be the issues of fiscal deficit to achieve unscrupulous goals of the politicians (Sarr, 2015). According to Bhatia (2016), India's capital expenditure is primarily related to building physical and social infrastructure. Therefore its deficit is on the higher side giving rise to increased borrowing and debt. Even the revenue expenditures in India are higher, which shows the government's inability to economise its resources.

The golden rule is that the government should borrow for investment alone and not for present spending and try and eliminate the deficit in revenue within five years and create a surplus fund in the revenue account (Bhatia, 2016). A study by Sarr (2015) has echoed macroeconomic indicators like annual growth of GDP and inflation to judge the budget credibility. In the examples of developing countries, there is an enhanced correlation of deviation from their projected revenues. This study (Sarr, 2015), used the following independent variables: GDP per capita, Population, Government effectiveness, Polity 2 Score, Centralisation, Legislature Strength, Oil rents (% GDP), ODA (%GNI). The dependent variables used were GDP growth, Inflation, Education, and Health. The results showed that fiscal transparency is very important for the excellence of its budget accomplishment in the education and health divisions. Oil is the most significant factor for deviations from the planned budget. Although most governments are transparent during the formulation phase, they do not publish the execution results regularly, thus poorly executing the budgets. This issue can be sorted by developing a robust financial management information system (FMIS) for the public, where year-end projected and actual reports on expenditures and receipts and the reasons for deviation from the projected budgets are published (Sarr, 2015).

2.2 Government Annual Budgets and Gender

Rubin and Bartle (2005) have reflected on a new perspective of the importance of gender equality on better social and economic development while formulating the budget and the allocation of resources and generating more gender-responsive revenue. For example, women's work lives are dotted with earning less than the men, holding more part-time jobs, unpaid domestic scenarios-resulting in fewer retirement funds and a longer average life span. Therefore it is time to implement a more gender-responsive budget and policies.

Higher Defence Budget as compared to Health Budget

In most developing countries, including India, the defence budget is higher than the health and education budgets. World Bank statistics (1985) have shown that low-income countries spend 18.5% on defence as compared to a mere 3.0 on health and 5.5% on education (Harris et al., 1988). In a study done by Sundaram *et al.* (2016), the 2016-17 allocation towards health was 39,571 crores. The annual budget expenditure for the defence was four lakh crores in 2018-19 as compared to health (56,000 crores), the absolute bottom of the pyramid!! (Union Budget, 2018). Although the allocation has increased from 10,680 crores in 2005-6 to 39,531 crores in 2016-17, the expenditure is 9259 crores in 2005-6 to 14,620 by the end of 2015. India spends a meagre 2.5% of its GDP on Health.

2.3 Higher Defence Budget as compared to Health Budget

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2.4 Budget 2018 highlights (including some earlier year comparisons)

- India's expenditure has increased from 3 lakhs to 24 lakhs from 2000 to 2018
- 16.5% of India's budget is attributed to defence (4 lakh crores)
- A fiscal deficit may be an oversight of the way the union budget is formulated and needs better Audits
- Health expenditure is a meagre 2.5 %of the GDP (54,660 crores)
- Borrowing fund was 26% of the Governments expenditure in 2018
- 24% in 2018 was spent on paying interest on the funds it borrowed
- 88% revenue expenditure is for paying salaries and administration costs, and 12% is on capital expenditure that includes subsidies and pension 7%
- The fiscal deficit has been 3.4% of its GDP, and 2.2% of GDP goes to revenue deficit
- Central Government's outstanding debt is 48.8% of the GDP
- 2013-15 were the only years were the actual expenditure was lower than the budgeted
- GST tax receipts, Corporation Tax and Income tax are significant sources of receipts by the government
- In India, prices of petrol, diesel and fertiliser sold to farmers and food under the PDS (public distribution system- 1,69, 323 crores was spent in 2018) is subsidised (Source: Union Budget, 2018, & Lok Sabha Secretariat, 2018)

3. CONCLUSION

This review has illustrated that India's annual budget concentrates more on the defence sector than health and education. It needs to come up with better strategies to counter its fiscal deficit. The budgets have various dimensions, and it is a tight-rope walk exercise for the finance minister to manage the country's financials. Unless fiscal discipline is enforced, the government will be forced to recourse to deficit financing through additional borrowings.

This increases the interest expenditure, which again leads to higher deficits. Thus, it is a case of a vicious circle. It is expected that the government should take some tough steps to come out of the vicious circle.

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